

Research Article

'Getam Guri': Revitalizing Cultural Identity in Contemporary Jewellery Design

Mohd Faiz Jalaludin¹

¹ Universiti Teknologi MARA; faiz457@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6386-914X>)

* Correspondence: faiz457@uitm.edu.my; 0192098245.

Abstract: *This study explores the potential of incorporating the traditional 'Getam Guri' motif into contemporary jewellery design to revitalize cultural identity. Historically significant motifs such as 'Getam Guri', rooted in Malaysian heritage, are often underutilized in modern design contexts, particularly in jewellery. This research adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative interviews with cultural experts and jewellery designers, alongside quantitative surveys targeting potential consumers and art enthusiasts. The aim is to assess perceptions, preferences, and the cultural significance of the 'Getam Guri' motif when applied to contemporary jewellery. The findings reveal a strong preference for jewellery that integrates cultural elements, with respondents expressing an appreciation for designs that reflect their heritage while maintaining modern appeal. Participants emphasized the potential of 'Getam Guri' motifs to inspire pride and preserve cultural identity in a way that resonates with a wider audience. This discussion highlights the multifaceted impacts of reintroducing traditional motifs in modern design, including fostering cultural preservation, enhancing the appeal of local craftsmanship, and supporting identity in both individual and collective contexts. In conclusion, the integration of 'Getam Guri' motifs in contemporary jewellery offers a strategic opportunity to preserve cultural heritage while engaging modern consumers, positioning this initiative as a meaningful approach to cultural sustainability and innovation in design.*

Keywords: Revival; Contemporary; Jewellery.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Revitalizing cultural identity involves reorganizing or enhancing cultural elements to make them more relevant and meaningful (Cambridge University Press, 2024). This concept is especially pertinent in the context of contemporary jewellery design, where the integration of traditional motifs like 'Getam Guri' offers a unique opportunity to reconnect with Malaysia's rich cultural heritage. 'Getam Guri', a traditional motif embedded in local artistry, holds deep cultural significance, yet its potential as a modern design element remains largely untapped. This study aims to reimagine 'Getam Guri' in contemporary jewellery design, transforming it from a traditional symbol into a modern expression of cultural identity.

The design thinking process, particularly the ideation phase—where ideas are generated and refined—is central to this transformation (Gavin Ambrose, 2010). By drawing inspiration from the intricate patterns and cultural narratives of 'Getam Guri', designers can evolve 2-dimensional motifs into 3-dimensional jewellery pieces that resonate with today's audience. This not only preserves the

cultural essence of the motif but also creates jewellery that tells a story, making it more than just an accessory but a symbol of heritage and identity.

The ‘Getam Guri’ motif, with its historical and artistic significance, serves as an ideal subject for this endeavor. Traditionally used in textile and decorative arts, the motif reflects a deep connection to nature and local mythology, making it an authentic representation of Malaysian cultural identity (Ithnin, 2020). By integrating these motifs into jewellery, this initiative aligns with broader efforts to preserve cultural heritage while creating meaningful, modern connections with both local and international audiences.

The process of incorporating ‘Getam Guri’ into contemporary jewellery design involves understanding cultural narratives, ideating unique designs, prototyping, and testing these creations to ensure they resonate with the target audience. By applying these design principles, the project seeks to produce jewellery that is not only aesthetically pleasing but also culturally significant. This initiative offers a strategic opportunity to revitalize cultural identity while supporting the preservation of heritage through modern design, positioning ‘Getam Guri’ as a symbol of both tradition and innovation in jewellery craftsmanship.

2. METHODOLOGY

This design research focuses on the ideation process, employing specific ideation methods to explore how the traditional ‘Getam Guri’ motif can be adapted into contemporary jewellery design. The methodology involves a series of steps that transform cultural and historical insights into innovative design outcomes (Karl Ulrich, 2012). Just as refining paddy into rice requires careful processing, product development involves turning ideas into marketable designs. A survey method was employed to evaluate the potential marketability, demand, and cultural relevance of ‘Getam Guri’-inspired jewellery (Priscilla A., 2005). Targeting jewellery designers, cultural practitioners, and consumers, the survey gathered insights on design preferences, the value of integrating cultural motifs, and commercial potential.

Figure 1. Survey on the necessity and importance of making ‘Getam Guri’ motif as a subject matter in contemporary jewellery design.

Would you be interested in purchasing jewellery that combines the *Getam Guri* motif if it were available in the market?

62 responses

Figure 2. Survey on the marketability potential of product inspired by 'Getam Guri'.

With cultural significance and market potential established, the ideation process began, aiming to create a jewellery collection that balances heritage with modern aesthetics. The researcher chose to develop pendants, earrings, and rings, as these items allow intricate detail while maintaining wearability and contemporary appeal. Jewellery as an art form provides various opportunities to incorporate cultural motifs, accommodating both two-dimensional patterns and three-dimensional sculpted elements (Radcliff, 2024).

The 'Getam Guri' motif, known for its floral and geometric designs, was selected for its cultural significance and adaptability. Traditionally used in textiles and carvings, 'Getam Guri' reflects the richness of Malaysian craftsmanship. The design was simplified to suit modern jewellery while preserving its cultural essence. Motifs were integrated into various jewellery pieces, including pendants with raised patterns, earrings reflecting floral symmetry, and rings with sculpted details—creating a contemporary, meaningful aesthetic.

Figure 3. The 'Getam Guri' flower is crafted into contemporary designs.

To enhance precision and design quality, the 'Getam Guri' motifs were digitized using CorelDRAW and 3-dimensional design software, which enabled precise adaptation for cutting and 3D printing. Before production, digital files were meticulously reviewed, focusing on aspects like element size, angle sharpness, and line overlaps, to ensure flawless output during the manufacturing process.

Figure 4. 'Getam Guri' motif is transformed and refined into a pendant design.

This methodology demonstrates the transformation of a traditional cultural motif into a modern product that aligns with contemporary aesthetics while preserving the cultural identity inherent in 'Getam Guri'. By integrating both 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional design software, this research not only aims to create visually appealing jewellery but also contributes to the revitalization and preservation of cultural heritage through innovative design.

3. FINDINGS

The researcher employed an ideation approach to design jewellery inspired by the 'Getam Guri' motif, guided by consumer survey insights. Findings indicate that 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery holds strong commercial potential, with its cultural depth drawing consumer interest and admiration. To capture this appeal, the researcher developed a collection of layered jewellery pieces, including pendants and earrings, which embody the 'Getam Guri' aesthetic in a modernized form.

Using both two-dimensional and three-dimensional design software, intricate details of the 'Getam Guri' motif were digitized and refined. For the final designs, polished gold simulation was employed in computer-generated realistic renderings, offering a premium visual representation of the jewellery. This polished gold finish, achieved through advanced rendering techniques, enhances the jewellery's sophisticated appeal, giving the appearance of luxurious, high-quality pieces. The designs also feature a layering technique where multiple elements are shaped and assembled, creating a three-dimensional representation of the 'Getam Guri' motif, adding depth and texture to each piece.

Figure 5. The 'Getam Guri' motif design is crafted into a three-dimensional form with enhanced detailing.

To further elevate the jewellery's aesthetic, select pieces incorporate gemstone settings, bringing elegance and a distinctive flair that connects the jewellery to its cultural roots. The integration of traditional motifs with modern design tools and realistic renderings positions 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery as a meaningful keepsake, celebrating Malaysian heritage. This design approach appeals to both local and international audiences, aligning with the broader initiative to preserve and promote cultural identity through innovative, high-quality jewellery design.

Figure 6. A design with intricate detailing in every part, adorned with gemstones.

Figure 7. A complete pendant design with chain, visualized virtually and ready for production.

4. DISCUSSION

The discussion emphasizes the cultural resonance of the 'Getam Guri' motif in modern jewellery, highlighting its potential to revitalize Malaysian cultural identity. Stakeholders and consumers expressed positive reactions toward 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery, underscoring the motif's value not only as an aesthetic element but as a representation of heritage and identity. The

enthusiasm for jewellery based on 'Getam Guri' reflects a broader appreciation for traditional arts and cultural motifs, suggesting that jewellery design can serve to preserve and celebrate cultural identity.

Beyond commercialization, this initiative has implications for cultural preservation. By integrating 'Getam Guri' motifs into jewellery, designers can provide a platform for cultural expression and knowledge transmission, creating pieces that celebrate Malaysian heritage while appealing to modern tastes. Introducing these motifs to a wider audience through wearable art can enhance both local and international appreciation for Malaysia's cultural symbols.

Modern technology, digital design software and simulation of realistic rendering, was crucial to achieving precise, intricate representations of the 'Getam Guri' motif. This blend of technology and tradition ensures that each piece retains the authenticity of 'Getam Guri' while catering to contemporary consumer preferences.

While the findings are promising, further research is needed. Future studies could explore the long-term impact of integrating cultural motifs into contemporary design, examining sustainability and cultural relevance over time. Additionally, investigating marketing strategies for 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery could enhance its cultural appeal and brand identity. Collaborations with local artisans could also foster ethical production practices, supporting local communities while ensuring sustainable design. Overall, while this research sheds light on the potential of 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery, there remains ample scope for continued exploration of its role in cultural preservation and contemporary design.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research highlights the potential of 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery to serve as a cultural symbol, promoting both Malaysian heritage and contemporary design innovation. The positive reception of jewellery based on the 'Getam Guri' motif reflects a widespread appreciation for traditional arts and their relevance in modern contexts. By integrating 'Getam Guri' into jewellery, designers can contribute to the preservation of cultural identity while introducing heritage to a broader, modern audience.

The incorporation of 3-dimensional design software has enhanced the precision and appeal of 'Getam Guri' jewellery, demonstrating how technology can work alongside traditional artistry to create culturally resonant, marketable products. This approach illustrates a commitment to blending tradition with innovation, positioning 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery as a meaningful bridge between heritage and contemporary aesthetics.

Additionally, 'Getam Guri'-based jewellery has the potential to strengthen cultural awareness and pride, both locally and internationally. By promoting cultural identity through wearable art, this initiative can inspire pride and foster a deeper connection to heritage within diverse communities.

While the research provides valuable insights, further studies could explore the sustainability and long-term impact of integrating traditional motifs into modern design. Collaborations with local artisans may also enhance authenticity and support ethical production. Overall, 'Getam Guri'-inspired jewellery represents a strategic step in revitalizing cultural identity, promoting heritage, and advancing cultural sustainability.

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